

Notes on the on the crevice-weaving spider *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 in southern Africa (Araneae: Filistatidae)

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ABSTRACT

Notes on the Crevice Weaving spider *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 are provided. The species was previously known only from Namibia but is also now known from South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle.

INTRODUCTION

The Filistatidae is represented by 19 genera and 185 species. Little work has been carried out on the filistatids of the Afrotropical Region, especially in southern Africa. From the Afrotropical Region four genera are known: *Afrofilistata* Benoit, 1968, *Andoharano* Lehtinen, 1967, *Pritha* Lehtinen, 1967 and *Sahastata* Benoit, 1968. However, from southern Africa only *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 is known. The species belongs to a small genus known prior to its description (Zonstein & Marusik 2015) exclusively from Madagascar

METHODS

The first author (AE) surveyed areas in Namibia. She found a tree at Grootfontein covered with webbing (Fig. 1). She later found similar webbing in other areas and sampled and also photographed the spiders (Figs 2-3). Voucher specimens were sent to the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council, as well as to Dr Marusik in Russia. He confirmed the identity of the spider as *Andoharano ansieae*, a species that had recently been described from Namibia.

Fig. 1. Tree at Grootfontein, Namibia covered with webbing (Photo: A. Eichhoff).

Figures 2-3. *Andoharano ansieae* specimens sampled from Namibia in areas covered with webbing (Photos: A. Eichhoff).

In South Africa the second author (ASD) received photographs from John Luyt of specimens sampled from a property near Gravelotte and Hoedspruit in the eastern part of Limpopo (Figs 4-7). The specimen was collected in a bathroom. A voucher specimen will be deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida.

TAXONOMY

Andoharano ansieae Zonstein & Marusik, 2015

Figures 2-9

Andoharano ansieae Zonstein & Marusik, 2015: 484, figs 1-12, 14-15.

Holotype male: NAMIBIA: Rundu-Kavango, Okavango, 17°57'S 19°43'E, V.1979, leg. M.E. Baddeley (MRAC 152150). Paratypes: 1 male 2 females, collected together with the holotype.

Body size: TL 3.15 mm male, 4.25 mm female. For a detailed description of the species see Zonstein & Marusik (2015). They mentioned the long hair on the male palp. Palp with all segments covered with long hairs; hairs on patella, tibia and cymbium longer than corresponding segments on legs; femur longer than patella+tibia, with long suberected ventral hairs, and decumbent dorsal hairs, longest hairs about half of the segment length; patella twice longer than wide, with long and dense dorsal hairs; tibia subconical, distal edge wider than proximal, and wider than femur width; dorsal hairs sparse in basal half and dense in distal part, some of hairs almost twice longer than tibia; cymbium short, its height shorter than diameter of bulb, apical part with dense brush of hairs forming kind of forelock hanging over the bulb, hairs 3× longer than cymbium (Figs 8-9) (Zonstein & Marusik 2015).

BEHAVIOUR

Filistatids are nocturnal, living in tubular silk-lined retreats in crevices in rocks or walls. They have signal-webs very similar to the Segestriidae, consisting of a tubular retreat made in crevices in rocks and walls, with trip-lines radiating from the entrance (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

In Namibia they were found in webs made on walls, in and outside houses. During the day they hide under their webs, or they creep into the tube-like retreats that are integrated in the catch web, which are often spun on the edge of the web. At night they sit outside on the web, waiting for prey.

The sticky cribellate webs gather dust look dusty and untidy, with several round exit/entrance holes that lead to the actual retreats of the spiders. Every spider has its own "place"; they live solitarily, but there can be many individuals under one huge area of catch web on a tree or a wall, forming a colony.

Webs can be seen on tree trunks, on walls, old switchboards, on window handles, in the house on and behind decorative articles, behind foot skirting, cupboards, on window sills in the house. During the day these spiders sit in their retreats in the dark. When they live on trees, their retreats are under the bark (Fig. 10). They guard their egg sacs (Fig. 11), which are covered loosely by a sheet.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & JOCQUÉ, R. 1997. *African spiders, an identification manual*. Biosystematics Division, ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. Handbook 9, 392 pp.

Figures 4-7. *Andoharano ansieae* specimens from Gravelotte (Photos: J. Luyt)

Figures 8-9. *Andoharano ansieae*, male palp. 8. Anterior view (Photo: J. Luyt); 9. Palp (from Zonstein & Marusik 2015).

Figures 10-11. *Andoharano ansieae*. 10. Webbing on bark; 11. Egg sac (Photos: A. Eichhoff).

ZONSTEIN, S.L. & MARUSIK, Y.M. 2015. The first record of *Andoharano* Lehtinen, 1967 (Araneae: Filistatidae) from mainland Africa. *African Invertebrates* 56: 483-489.